

Characterization of Al-6061 based metal matrix composite fabricated by stir casting route and modified by friction stir processing (FSP)

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Abstract

As 6061 Al-alloy possess high strength to weight ratio and having good corrosion resistance, it is used for automobile parts although having this advantage it has poor wear resistance which limits its application however metal matrix composite (MMC) in which hard ceramic particle such as SiC is dispersed leads to good improvement in wear and stiffness but in expense of ductility moreover uniform dispersion is very difficult in stir casting route so Friction stir processing (FSP) is done afterward since FSP is a novel technique and can be used for surface modification in composites by microstructure refinement and mechanical property enhancement. In this work Study has been carried out to explain the effect of FSP on the Al-6061/SiC_p (MMC) which is fabricated by stir casting technique, Aluminium matrix composites (AMCs) reinforced with 2% vol. SiC particle of size (20-160) μm which was then hot rolled at 420°C to minimize casting defects such as porosity later on modified by FSP. FSP has been conducted with 750, 1525 rpm of tool speed having cylindrical pin profile and keeping other variables such as traverse speed (50mm/min), tool geometry to be constant. In the present work the comparison of properties between cast Al-6061 alloy, SiC reinforced AMC (without FSP) and SiC reinforced AMC (with FSP) has been carried out. Microstructure, wear property, tensile properties and Vickers hardness test were investigated and characterization of the composite is done using X-ray diffraction, optical and scanning electron microscopy. X-ray diffraction patterns of Al-6061/SiC_p AMCs revealed the presence of SiC particles without formation of any other intermetallic compounds. Primary results showed more homogeneous distribution of SiC_p in FSP zone than base metal and an improvement in mechanical properties which is due to grain refinement. Significant improvement in the ductility was observed after FSP when compared with cast composite.

Keywords : FSP, Nanocomposites, 6061 Al-alloy